

THE ROLE OF LITERATURE LESSONS IN EDUCATING YOUTH IN THE SPIRIT OF NATIONAL VALUES

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the author provides some evidence and their theoretical basis for educating our youth in the spirit of devotion to our national and universal values. Factors necessary to teach young people to think freely, to help them understand the meaning of life, to form self-control and self-control are identified.

The implementation of serious measures to restore national values in our country is of great importance in the revival of our spirituality. Today, the world recognizes that our national values are being restored. In particular, the events dedicated to such great figures as Sahibqiron Amir Temur, Mirzo Ulugbek, Bahauddin Naqshband, the anniversaries of the cities of Bukhara and Khiva, and the participation of representatives from more than 50 countries of the world in symposiums are a vivid example of this.

As is known, traditions are an invaluable spiritual wealth created in the process of the historical formation and development of the people and passed down from ancestors to generations as a sacred heritage. Preserving and perfecting customs that have become one of the main signs of the nation remains the sacred duty of each generation.

In order for traditions to survive, first of all, they must be mastered by the youth, the creators of our future. The revival of traditional folk holidays remains a very important event in the history of Uzbek culture. Because holidays are a large and important form of culture that embodies the best aspects of life. In this way, the revival of ancient holidays has created the basis for the revival of the most valuable aspects of folk culture. When it comes to the revival of folk traditions, it is necessary to pay special attention to folk games, which play an important role in the development of youth. The most ancient traditional, many cultural forms of our ancestors, dance, theater and sports rituals originated from these games and have been a means of healing for our ancestors in the historical process.

It is clear that if love for the homeland does not burn in the heart, if the heart does not burn with love for it, if the strings of filial duty and responsibility for the homeland do not move in the body, even if it is said that "My homeland is my place of worship, my place of success," the love and loyalty in us will seem like a kind of abstract feeling. Today, everything we do is done for the happiness and well-being of our youth and their bright future. A well-mannered, educated, intelligent, hard-working, and faithful child is the greatest wealth not only of parents, but also of the entire society.

In this process, the factors that raise national spirituality, national consciousness, national consciousness, and national feeling to perfection in each person are transferred to the process of activity. Our society has its own real opportunities to implement these lofty goals. First of all, in a free and independent Motherland, conditions have been created that lead the people to prosperity and, in a certain sense, guarantee a decent life. Our state has grown up with selfless, hardworking, highly qualified forces with high organizational potential. In their image and activities, there is a stable essence and creative power of national spirituality. Such people with a stable national spirituality protect the interests of their people, nation, and homeland under any circumstances, are people who can demonstrate the national spirituality of our people in their activities, demonstrate the potential of the nation, the value, honor, and glory of the Motherland among nations and states. The main tasks of instilling national values in young people through extracurricular activities should focus on the following:

Firstly, to teach young people to think freely, to help them understand the meaning of life, to form self-management and control, to develop a purposeful approach to their personal lives, to instill a sense of unity of plan and action;

Secondly, to introduce students to national, universal values, the rich spiritual heritage of our Motherland, to form their requirements for acquiring cultural and secular knowledge, to form skills, to cultivate and enrich them, and to form aesthetic concepts;

Thirdly, to identify the knowledge and creative potential of each teenager, to develop them, to implement them in various fields of human activity. To create conditions for the emergence and further support of the creativity and talent of young people;

Fourthly, to form the norms of humane etiquette (understanding each other, kindness, compassion, the ability to fight racial and national discrimination), to widely use such educational tools as manners;

Fifth, to teach our youth to think freely and independently. Extracurricular educational activities complement the educational process in their free time, based on the interests, desires, wishes and needs of students and young people. The organization of these processes creates an opportunity to increase the creative abilities and initiative of young people.

It is necessary to determine the daily time budget of today's youth: the sociology of time outside of school and classes (except for household chores for unorganized youth) and, on this basis, develop and implement measures for the effective organization of extracurricular activities. When organizing extracurricular spiritual and educational activities: competitions, clubs, amateur art, meetings, debates, sports competitions, round tables, trainings and other events, the following methods should be effectively used: persuasion, example-setting, learning, practice, encouragement, negative attitude towards vices, discussions, observation, training, collective creative activities, "ideological situation", dynamic, imitative, role-playing games and other similar methods.

Love for books in Uzbek families, their preservation and reading have become virtues that have gained importance in the spiritual development of our people. Because in a person's self-education, a book serves as both a source of knowledge and, to a certain extent, a mirror for seeing oneself, comparing, imitating, discussing, and arguing. Reading forms the ability to observe and reflect, sharpens and deepens the mind.

In extracurricular activities, it is important to encourage young people to read books, to create opportunities for them to work on themselves using books. It is necessary to involve students and young people in getting acquainted with historical places, antiquities, monuments, and shrines and studying them.

Based on today's requirements, work is being carried out to further improve the activities of museums. Organizing visits of students to museums should become a tradition. It is necessary to organize various educational events such as "My State", "My People", "My Homeland", "We are no less than anyone, and we will never be less", and ensure the active participation of students and unorganized youth in them.

It is necessary to focus on forming an attitude towards national and universal values, which are the main principles of the idea of national independence, by teaching young people to behave in the neighborhood, respect for elders, honor for the younger, and a sense of solidarity in good and bad times, based on their participation in weddings, public celebrations, and holidays.

The current national spirituality and values of the Uzbek people are a continuation of the national spirituality of the past, and include friendship, hospitality, humanity, moral purity, generosity, courtesy, imagination, kindness, cleanliness, cheerfulness, good nature, courage, sincerity, generosity, thrift, love for the homeland and people, honesty, piety, truthfulness, honesty, honor, correctness, patience, restraint, self-sufficiency, respect for parents and elders, hard work, respect for the past, honesty, faith, national pride, patriotism, nationalism, etc. Today, instilling these in the minds of young people is the main task of every parent and educator.

The customs, traditions, and rituals of our people are of great educational importance. The love, reasonable attitude, proper communication, courtesy, and respect of people for each other reflect the inner beauty, rich spiritual and mental image of our people. Most importantly, the feelings and qualities of our people, such as kindness, generosity, hospitality, courtesy, kindness, thoughtfulness, sincerity, honesty, discipline, hard work, self-control, thrift, patience and contentment, serve as an example in the upbringing of a harmonious generation today.

Based on the results of our research, the following can be proposed in terms of educating young people in the spirit of loyalty to national values:

1. Organizing excursions for unorganized youth and students to historical monuments, educational institutions, art palaces, and structures erected during the period of independence;
2. Revitalizing the work of local history and history clubs;
3. To organize creative evenings and meetings with famous artists, lawyers, educators and scientists, labor veterans, and health workers in order to form the spiritual, economic, legal, environmental, labor, and aesthetic culture of the youth of the community based on universal and national values;
4. To organize meetings of unorganized youth and their students in the neighborhoods with famous people such as poets and writers, state and public figures, and labor veterans.

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